

Large neural networks, driven by natural language processing, are making strides forward in artificial intelligence (AI). However, their learning phase requires large computing power and has high energy requirements. Moreover, these models are mostly in private hands.

Gigantic Transformers and mega-models: The next El Dorado for AI? or Is “the bigger, the better” the path to AGI?

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Artificial intelligence (AI) is everywhere in the news, with personal assistants being perhaps its most visible expression for consumers. While image recognition was behind the renewal of AI in 2012, natural language processing (NLP) is the next “big thing” driving research and competition. It has delivered surprisingly good results in many areas, mainly with gigantic networks based on “transformers”. It is also an embodiment of the battle between the United States and China (and between large companies) to get the most powerful artificial neural network.

Key insights

- The size of the top-performing neural networks is generally increasing in line with their performance. The consequence of this is that computing power is becoming less and less affordable, while having an increasingly large energy footprint.
- Natural language processing and deep neural networks that mimic cognitive attention [1] (such as “transformers”) are now driving innovation in high-end neural networks. These neural networks require tremendous processing power and large amounts of data for their learning phase.
- This might lead to short-term “assistants” in various domains, such as producing office documents or programming code.
- Is it also the path to more generic AI, or even towards artificial general intelligence (AGI) systems?
- In between impressive and accurate results, they also generate totally crazy answers, and it is challenging to easily and automatically distinguish accurate from false answers. As with any tool made by humans, we should use them pragmatically.
- Transformers and attention-based models, initially tuned for NLP, are now used for a wide range of applications, including image processing.
- Simulation of virtual environments is starting to be used to train deep neural networks (for example, NVIDIA’s Omniverse [2], Microsoft Azure’s digital twins [3]).

Key recommendations

- Europe should not be left behind in the AI race, and should offer researchers easily accessible computational resources for advanced deep-learning models. For very high-end models, like GPT-3 and its successors, a pan-national structure like CERN could be established, with access to a range of exascale deep-learning resources.
- Europe should prioritize AI research that results in real social value, guided by ethical principles. As uses of these advanced models can be beneficial or can cause new threats (deep fakes that are indistinguishable from reality, generating unrealistic or false answers), people should be educated to use these tools in a responsible way and ethical committees should analyse the various usages and steer research towards augmenting the “positive” effects. Research in the field of automatic detection of deepfakes should also be supported.
- In parallel, new models that are efficient but smaller should be developed, or a federation of smaller AI implementations, where interoperability is key (like the World Wide Voice Web [4] initiated by Stanford University)
- These federations of intertwined AI examples should be based on open-source communication and orchestration protocols, taking into account not only functional requirements, but also non-functional ones (latency, energy cost, reliability of results, ...).
- Consumer use of these systems should be encouraged, to decrease digital illiteracy in Europe and assist citizens in their everyday lives (See the HiPEAC Vision article “‘Digels’, digital *genius loci* engines to guide and protect users in the ‘next web’”).
- Hybrid systems using both direct knowledge (expert systems, algorithmic approaches) and deep-learning techniques should be developed to get the full benefit of all approaches.

What is “artificial intelligence”?

AI, and more specifically deep learning, was first a necessity for the major technology companies in the United States (Google – Alphabet, Amazon, Meta, Apple and Microsoft, the “GAMAM”) and in China (Baidu, Alibaba, Tencent and Xiaomi, the “BATX”). For example, it allowed such companies to check if the millions of pictures uploaded everyday were “correct” (a typical Facebook deep-learning use case). These companies have all the necessary resources for deep learning: large and powerful computing infrastructure for learning and managing large databases, large sets of data and ways to attract the best scientists.

However, as discussed in previous editions of the HiPEAC Vision, AI is not new: the term artificial intelligence was coined by John McCarthy during a workshop at Dartmouth College in 1956 and developed in several directions, the two main ones being:

- 1) Symbolic (or algorithmic) AI where high-level “symbolic” (human-readable) representations of problems are transformed by explicit (logic) rules, generally generated by humans (either directly, applying algorithms, or indirectly, being extracted and organized in expert systems, which use a network of production rules). The “deductions” of the AI system can therefore be followed and explained, but all the “rules” have to be put in the systems beforehand. As computers can process large sets of data quickly, this can create the illusion of “intelligence” because of the size and the speed it applies rules/algorithms to the data.
- 2) “Connectionist” or “artificial neural-network-based” (now extended to deep learning) AI. Here, simple models of the neurons of the brain – originating from the work of Warren McCulloch and Walter Pitts in 1943 – are assembled in networks. The “neurons” are connected by “weights” to simulate biological synapses, and the purpose of the network is mainly the result of the various values of the synapses.

During the “learning” phase, these weights are determined by repetitive presentations of patterns at the input of

the network, and what it means at the output. These multiple presentations set the weights so that, at the end, the network associates the desired output with the input. This is called “supervised” learning because the inputs are labelled with the correct responses the neural network should give at the output. The resulting neural network is not only an associative memory: it can also give similar results to input data that are “similar” (not too distant) and this is called generalization. It can then classify (during what is called the “inference” phase) input patterns it has never seen during the learning phase. The “knowledge” of these networks is therefore extracted from the data rather than being explicitly given by the programmer.

There are also other ways to train those neural networks without a supervised approach. For example, they can be trained with unsupervised learning, where the network determines its output from different inputs which then do not need to be labelled and tries to automatically divide entries into different classes, or with reinforcement learning, which focuses on predicting a reward. Self-supervised learning is another of the possible options.

Reinforcement learning was used to train DeepMind’s AlphaGo program and its successors, like Alpha Zero, which, in a few hours and without any knowledge of the field except the rules, beat all its predecessors (and humans) both at the game of Go and at chess. The latest update,

MuZero, did not even have to be taught the rules; it observes the results of its actions and therefore improves itself.

“The new system tries first one action, then another, learning what the rules allow, at the same time noticing the rewards that are proffered – in chess, by delivering check-mate; in Pac-Man, by swallowing a yellow dot. It then alters its methods until it hits on a way to win such rewards more readily – that is, it improves its play. Such learning by observation is ideal for any AI that faces problems that can’t be specified easily” [5].

“the MuZero algorithm, [...] by combining a tree-based search with a learned model, achieves superhuman performance in a range of challenging and visually complex domains, without any knowledge of their underlying dynamics. The MuZero algorithm learns an iterable model that produces predictions relevant to planning: the action-selection policy, the value function and the reward” [6].

Other approaches are also being developed, such as generative adversarial networks (GANs) that put different networks in competition.

The renaissance of AI in 2012 was triggered by the superior performance of the deep-learning approach (a special form of formal neural networks) for image classification, initiated by the work of Hinton et al. [7] in that same year with their “deep” neural network that they called “Supervision”. As deep learning provides relatively good (or, at least, good enough)

results when applied to various application domains, with relatively low human effort, it has really taken off since then; now it is at the top of the curve of expectations. From a marketing point of view, companies feel obliged to apply these technologies to their products to keep up with the trend. Even methods and approaches that have been used for some time are now jostling for position under the umbrella of “artificial intelligence”.

The rise of large models

A new (r)evolution came in 2017 with the paper “Attention Is All You Need” [8] which introduced “transformers”, a special form of deep neural networks that work on sequences of data, so their first use was for natural language processing. By feeding them with very large databases, they reached astonishing levels of performance.

This was confirmed in 2020, with the release of GPT-3 [9] [10], a system for natural language processing (NLP) using the “transformer” approach that has 175 billion parameters (the largest GPT-3 model – with 175B parameters – uses 96 attention layers, each with 96x 128-dimension heads). “[The] GPT-3 175B model required 3.14×10^{23} FLOPS” – that is, about 87 hours on an exascale machine, performing 10^{18} floating point operations per second – “of computing for training. Even at theoretical 28 TFLOPS for V100 (a Nvidia GPU) and lowest 3 year reserved cloud pricing we could find, this will take 355 GPU-years and cost \$4.6M for a single training run. Similarly, a single RTX 8000, assuming 15 TFLOPS, would take 665 years to run” [11].

“GPT-3 shows that language model performance scales as a power-law of model size, dataset size, and the amount of computation... GPT-3 demonstrates that a language model trained on enough data can solve NLP tasks that it has never encountered. That is, GPT-3 studies the model as a general solution for many downstream jobs without fine-tuning... GPT-3 175B is trained with 499 Billion tokens” (Figure 1).

GPT-3 exemplifies a growing collection of large models that can be applied in multiple domains, from generating source code from text specification (OpenAI Codex [13]) to the generation of images (DALL-E [14]) or short videos (Google

Imagen Video [15]) from text description. They are developing very rapidly. As an example, GPT-3 was released in May 2020; Meta’s OPT-175B [16], which was released just two years later in May 2022, delivers similar performance but with 1/7 of the CO₂ footprint of GPT-3.

Although initially OpenAI claimed it would release its results as open source, this has not been the case for GPT-3. Instead, in September 2020, Microsoft bought an exclusive licence to directly integrate GPT-3 into its own products [17]. Duplicating GPT-3 is not easy due to the large amount of data and the processing power required to train a similar network. However, there are several initiatives to release models with similar performance in the open source domain, for example Hugging Face [18, 19].

Transformers were designed to work on sequences of information, for example speech, which results in some interesting side effects:

- If you hide part of the sequence and you ask the network to reproduce it, the hidden part of the sequence is the ground truth [20] and you don’t have to label the input sequence for the learning phase: the (hidden) data itself is the label. This self-supervised technique allows transformers to be fed with a minimally curated dataset.
- As transformers were trained to reconstruct sequences, they can generate predictions of possible future sequences from past and present data. It is how they are used to “create” new text, for example.
- The output of transformers depends on the context (the previous sequences), so past sequences can drive the direction in which the transformer will generate new sequences. So the initial sequence “programs” the transformer and drives it to generate similar output. This is how a transformer trained on a huge database can perform what seem to be different tasks, simply by changing the initialization sequence in “inference” mode: it can

Dataset	# Tokens (Billions)
Total	499
Common Crawl (filtered by quality)	410
WebText2	19
Books1	12
Books2	55
Wikipedia	3

Figure 1: the dataset used for the training of GPT-3 [11]

Human: Do you know the HiPEAC vision document ?
 AI: Yes, I am familiar with the HiPEAC vision document.
 Human: Summarize the last HiPEAC vision document in 500 words.
 AI: The HiPEAC vision document is a roadmap for the future of computing. It sets out six key areas where computing will have a major impact:

1. Virtual reality and augmented reality
2. Artificial intelligence
3. The internet of things
4. Quantum computing
5. Blockchain technology
6. Cloud computing

Each of these areas is set to have a profound impact on the way we live and work in the years ahead. HiPEAC is committed to driving innovation in these areas and ensuring that computing remains a key driver of economic growth and social progress.

Figure 2: Asking an AI program (OpenAI) about the HiPEAC Vision, with the following parameters: Engine: text-davinci-002 (A follow-up of GPT-3 [12]), Max tokens: 150, Temperature: 0, Top p: 1, Frequency penalty: 0.0, Presence penalty: 0.0, Stop sequence: \n)

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summarize text, translate it into another language, or even include a programming language, leading, for example, to Codex [13], which can generate (in some cases) running code from textual specifications. Codex powers GitHub's programming aid Copilot [21].

As noted above, this domain is evolving at a swift pace; for example, OpenAI DALL-E was released on 2 April 2022 (rapidly followed by DALL-E 2), a tool capable of creating realistic images and art from a description in natural language. Google made its Imagen tool public in May 2022 with similar functionalities, and by October 2022 the company had released Imagen Video. With this tool, Google claims to be able to produce videos with a resolution of 1280 x 768 pixels with 24 frames per second from text. The website [15] features videos such as "a teddy bear running around New York", "a drone flies over a snow-covered rainforest", "a teddy bear does the dishes".

Google Imagen Video was made public just after Meta unveiled Make-A-Video. This tool, presented on 29 September 2022, also allows you to transform text into video. The system can also create videos from images or take existing videos and create new, similar ones.

All this is evidence of the competition between OpenAI (which has links with

Microsoft), Google, Meta and NVIDIA (with its Megatron [22]) in the field of large models and transformers. The size (number of parameters) of these large networks has been increasing over time, as shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

The computing power required to train these networks makes it difficult for small companies or universities in Europe to be able to compete, without even taking into account the size of the database required. That implies that Europe can only use pre-trained networks, without knowing the exact content of the learning database and without having knowhow in building such megamodels. The computing power required is not unavailable in Europe, but it would require prioritization and organization to allow computing resources to be devoted to such training.

As an example, the blog [25] gives more details on the requirements of PaLM [26], from Google: "PaLM has 540B parameters and is 3x bigger than GPT-3 175B parameters. It is likely the most expensive model ~\$10M [27] (2.5 yottaFLOPS) vs GPT-3 ~\$5M [11]. The PaLM training dataset consists [of] 780B tokens of high-quality text (~100B human days), social media 50%, webpages 27%, books 13%, wikipedia 4%, code 5%, news 1%. It is a private non-reproducible dataset, while MT-NLG [28] 339B

is reproducible but non-hosted. The PaLM Training Requirements are ~17 TB of RAM, 2.5 yottaFLOPS (1024) needed for training. It uses 2 TPU v4 Pod clusters connected via [a] data center network, with each Pod ~1 exaflop/s: 768 hosts, 3072 TPU v4 chips."

We can figure that this was only possible because of the availability of the fourth generation of TPU [29] accelerator chips from Google. TPUs are proprietary accelerators dedicated to accelerated learning and inference of deep neural networks; they are aggregated into "pods" of 4096 TPU v4. "[O]ne TPU pod of v4 chips can deliver more than one exaflops of floating point performance", according to Google CEO Sundar Pichai as quoted in [29]. These performance metrics are based on Google's custom floating-point format, called "Brain Floating Point Format," or bfloat16.

Until recently, it seemed that OpenAI's Jared Kaplan and colleagues were correct when they concluded [30] that "our results strongly suggest that larger models will continue to perform better, and will also be much more sample efficient than has been previously appreciated. Big models may be more important than big data."

But there is evidence that increasing the size of the megamodels is now reaching a plateau. At the time of writing, Google's PaLM seems to be the biggest model with

Figure 3: The increasing size of megamodels. Image: Bain & Company (from [23])

Figure 4: Evolution of the computing power necessary to train megamodels (from [24])

540B parameters. Megatron-Turing NLG, built by NVIDIA and Microsoft end of 2021 was already using 530B parameters, so more than three times the size of GPT-3 [31]. However, in term of performance in benchmarks, Megatron-Turing NLG is not the best; smaller models, like Chinchilla (70B) [32] perform significantly better than MT-NLG (and GPT-3, Gopher) across different tasks. Chinchilla is 7.5 times smaller than MT-NLG but was trained with four times more data. As stated in [32], “[c]urrent large language models are “significantly undertrained,” which is a consequence of blindly following the scaling hypothesis – making models larger isn’t the only way toward improved performance”.

This seems to show that current models are oversized, and should be trained with many more parameters, which will require not only more computing power but also more data. This reinforces the problem of availability and limits the number of organizations able to collect enough data and access the processing power to efficiently train these megamodels, not to mention the number of researchers.

The size of the databases for the training makes it difficult to curate and audit these models in detail, leading to networks with

Figure 5: The computing requirements of various models, from [25]

Table 1 | Current LLMs. We show five of the current largest dense transformer models, their size, and the number of training tokens. Other than LaMDA (Thoppilan et al., 2022), most models are trained for approximately 300 billion tokens. We introduce Chinchilla, a substantially smaller model, trained for much longer than 300B tokens.

Model	Size (# Parameters)	Training Tokens
LaMDA (Thoppilan et al., 2022)	137 Billion	168 Billion
GPT-3 (Brown et al., 2020)	175 Billion	300 Billion
Jurassic (Lieber et al., 2021)	178 Billion	300 Billion
Gopher (Rae et al., 2021)	280 Billion	300 Billion
MT-NLG 530B (Smith et al., 2022)	530 Billion	270 Billion
Chinchilla	70 Billion	1.4 Trillion

Figure 6: Relation between size and number to training tokens, from [33]

unknown characteristics. The training cost is so large that even large companies do not carry out training several times to tune the parameters or to correct errors. This leaves the evolution of AI technology in very few (private) hands. Furthermore, in contrast to the current advance of science, their results are not reproducible because of the lack of data and processing power, and the resulting megamodels often demonstrate bias due to the lack of retraining (due to the cost) when an error is detected. The lack of transparency is compounded by the fact that companies often publish papers showing only their advances, not the models themselves.

In fact, most companies or organizations do not release their trained networks into the scientific community, certainly for strategic reasons (e.g. OpenAI which preferred to license its GPT-3 to Microsoft) but also, they say, because they think that they can be “*misused and become dangerous*” (as noted in [34], for example). Recent text-to-image generators have safety rules embedded that limit their ability to generate explicit, violent or other sensitive images. The Stability AI text-to-image model Stable Diffusion, for example, embeds such rules; it was released to the public [35], leading to a large community working with it, enhancing and improving it. It can now even run on laptops. As noted above, Hugging Face [36] is an initiative where open-source models can be found and used, together with some GitHub repositories (e.g. for Stable Diffusion [37] or for Galactica [38] from Meta AI).

Large models in practice

It is also interesting to observe the reactions to these models, some of which speak

to the wider social issues caused by putting AI into the public arena without necessarily taking the consequences into account. Stable Diffusion generated concerns about copyright, given that it explicitly used artists’ work to generate particular styles [39]. More broadly, the use of image or text generation has given rise to concerns of disinformation being spread – including fake artefacts used to rewrite the historical record – leading to a growing inability on the part of users to distinguish truth from fiction and undermining trust in the public sphere [40].

AI models have also been shown to advance negative stereotypes due to their uncontrolled learning phase. The Microsoft chatbot “Tay” was removed in 2016 from Twitter after few days because its outputs became offensive due to the input of humans. The bot was supposed to learn from conversations and become smarter, but it was a success with racists, trolls, and online troublemakers. As explained in [41]: *“It’s important to note that Tay’s racism is not a product of Microsoft or of Tay itself. Tay is simply a piece of software that is trying to learn how humans talk in a conversation. Tay doesn’t even know it exists or what racism is. The reason it spouted garbage is because racist humans on Twitter quickly spotted a vulnerability – that Tay didn’t understand what it was talking about – and exploited it.”*

An interesting example of some of these issues is the demo website of Galactica [42], a language model from Meta AI trained on 48 million papers, textbooks, reference material, compounds, proteins and other sources of scientific knowledge. This was also retired after few days in November 2022, because a lot of complaints about

it, spotting mainly weaknesses [43] and not the potential benefit of such systems to help scientists from information overload. Like any other large language models, Galactica generates nonsense and data that are not true [44], but it can also generate interesting insights. Perhaps part of the problem came from the fact that the model was not always perceived for what it was, just another tool; this certainly needs education and pragmatism. Due to the fact it generates correct sentences, people anthropomorphized it and assumed it had human-level understanding; in fact, like Tay, Galactica does not understand what it is talking about.

It is also true that in scientific publications (the domain targeted by Galactica), every word and every sign has a meaning, and everything generated should be verified for accuracy. However, the authoritative tone of Galactica’s outputs suggested they were correct, even when they were wildly wrong [44]. It should be noted that the Galactica website included a disclaimer about the limitations of the model (Figure 7), but even this was criticized for itself anthropomorphizing the model (using the word “hallucinate”, which is common in the machine-learning sphere, for example [45]).

Unlike Tay, scientists who would like to experiment with Galactica (and make more effort than using a website) can still do so because it was released as open source [38]. However, again, due to the size of the database, and the compute power required, it would be difficult to retrain such a big model, and most researchers will only use it as is.

All this would suggest that, in the domain of megamodels, progress is in the hands of very few companies, lacking reproducibility of results and potentially lacking the appropriate safeguards before launching a complex tool in hands of the wider public [46].

Future directions

As noted above, some researchers have also suggested that Jared Kaplan’s prediction [30] needs to be revisited. That is, size is not the only thing that matters, most current models are oversized, and there are

Figure 7: Warning on the Galactica web site [42]

ways to reduce their size with similar, or even better efficiency. However, according to the figures outlined in the paper from Hoffmann et al [33] (see Figure 8), only a few companies and organizations would be able to develop even more efficient models. These models will need even more computing power for training and more tokens, but, as their number of parameters decrease for similar performance, their use in inference will be easier.

In terms of energy and computing power, it is important to consider the complete lifetime of a model, not just its training phase. If a model requires more compute power (therefore energy) during training but less during inference, and it is later used in billions of smartphones (e.g. for translation) for example, the overall cost might be lower. Reducing the number of parameters and the computing and storage requirements would allow models to be used in embedded systems.

Hopefully there will be improvements in algorithms, in data coding (now some

Parameters	FLOPs	FLOPs (in <i>Gopher</i> unit)	Tokens
400 Million	1.92e+19	1/29,968	8.0 Billion
1 Billion	1.21e+20	1/4,761	20.2 Billion
10 Billion	1.23e+22	1/46	205.1 Billion
67 Billion	5.76e+23	1	1.5 Trillion
175 Billion	3.85e+24	6.7	3.7 Trillion
280 Billion	9.90e+24	17.2	5.9 Trillion
520 Billion	3.43e+25	59.5	11.0 Trillion
1 Trillion	1.27e+26	221.3	21.2 Trillion
10 Trillion	1.30e+28	22515.9	216.2 Trillion

Figure 8: Optimum number of tokens from training megamodels, and the corresponding compute power, according to [33]

computations can be performed in float8, a new data format supported by recent NVIDIA GPUs) and in accelerator performances. Algorithmic improvement is a key factor driving the advance of AI: “Since 2012 the amount of compute needed to train a neural net to the same performance on ImageNet1 classification has been decreasing by a factor of 2 every 16 months [47].”

Finding the right set of hyperparameters is also an approach that could result in better networks, and new techniques are

being developed to find better parameters, like uTransfer [48]. This could reduce the size of a megamodel while maintaining its levels of performance. Quantization and pruning techniques are also important to reduce the computing cost; see the HiPEAC Vision 2023 article “AI for better integrations between the physical and cyber world: Embedded AI” for further details.

The combination of learning and explicit knowledge can also be used to improve the performance of AI systems, and to verify if

Figure 9: Decrease of the required computing power to train a Deep Neural Network for similar performances, from [47]

their results are within “acceptable” bounds (as these bounds are generally defined by rules, equivalent to “laws” for humans, well managed by systems other than deep neural networks). Multimodality [49] is also an interesting approach that could result in both more accurate and more understandable results.

New approaches could also be explored, just as transformers were an evolution of recurrent neural networks to process sequential input data. We have seen above the performance of large, monolithic networks, like in the centralized brain in mammals. But some other structures, like distributed ones, also show interesting emerging properties.

Is there proof in nature that other brain structures – different to those of humans or evolved mammals – can also show high levels of intelligence? Yes, for example in octopi. They are as intelligent as some mammals, for example they can use tools, yet they have a different brain structure: they have the equivalent to eight spinal cords, one running down each arm. The sequencing of the octopus genome shows that they possess brain-building genes called protocadherins, which were previously thought to exist only in vertebrates [50]. “Protocadherin diversity provides a mechanism for regulating the short-range interactions needed for the assembly of local

Figure 10: Image generated by an AI [53] with the trigger words: friendly octopus brain , with computer on each arm. realistic

neural circuits, which is where the greatest complexity in the cephalopod nervous system appears. The importance of local neuropil interactions, rather than long-range connections, is probably due to the limits placed on axon density and connectivity by the absence of myelin, as thick axons are then required for rapid high-fidelity signal conduction over long distance” [51]. “While humans have about 60 protocadherins, the octopus genome was found to have 168, nearly three times the neural wiring capacity than humans”. [50]

“The research team also hypothesized that cephalopod neurons don’t function well over long distances, forcing octopi to evolve a “short-range brain” that works better in bursts and isn’t operationally centralized [52].” [50]

While clearly not proof, this suggests that a federation of smaller neural networks, faster and denser, can exhibit similar behaviour to a monolithic one (as far we can consider that the brain of mammals is monolithic...). This idea can also be observed in the “swarm” or “collective” intelligence in ant or bee colonies.

Therefore, research and developing distributed and decentralized federated learning techniques could be one approach to obtaining good performance levels, by harnessing the contributions of a collection of smaller networks working together. This could also have advantages in terms of privacy (data remains local, only high-level concepts are exchanged) and efficiency: if a good result is identified by the local network, less communication and less overall computing power is used. If a good result is not found, we can define systems where resources (i.e. a federation of local AIs) are triggered until a good result is found, resulting in optimal resource usage.

Conclusion

We have seen that megamodels have very interesting properties, but they are not yet well tuned and their application can be problematic. They require an enormous amount of data and processing power for their training, meaning that only a few companies and organizations are able to drive their development. Progress is in the hands of very few companies without reproducibility of their results by the scientific community. Most of them are not available

for inspection and analysis (they are not available in open source, for example) and are only accessible through (paid) application programming interfaces (APIs).

Europe as a whole should take this into consideration, and be able to develop models tuned for European languages, culture and ethics. This is perhaps more an organizational problem than a scientific one: a “large instrument”, or piece of infrastructure, could be created to develop those megamodels, build large, curated databases for their training and have efficient computing power to develop them in reasonable amount of time (perhaps similar to the model of the CERN for nuclear research). At a different level, perhaps appropriate regulation should be considered to ensure that only AI models with appropriate safeguards may be developed and deployed for the citizens of Europe.

If European researchers cannot experiment and test their ideas at scale, they will lose their place in the scientific race of AI, meaning that Europe might be dependent on megamodels built by non-European companies or countries. On the other hand, research should be done on innovative solutions to reduce the computing requirements of those megamodels, and finding new innovative approaches to reach similar results with different, but more efficient structures.

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